

CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC CEREBRAL ISCHEMIA AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF THE COMBINED COURSE OF HYPERTENSION AND ATHEROSCLEROSIS DEPENDING ON THE COURSE STAGE

G.S.Rakhimbaeva

Department of Neurology with Medical Psychology
Tashkent Medical Academy
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

N.A.Mirkhaetova

Department of Neurology with Medical Psychology
Tashkent Medical Academy
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article discusses clinical and neurological characteristics of patients with chronic cerebral ischemia against the background of the combined course of hypertension and atherosclerosis depending on the course stage.

Keywords: neurological characteristics, patients, chronic cerebral, ischemia, course of hypertension, atherosclerosis.

Relevance

One of the most common diseases of the central nervous system is chronic cerebral ischemia (CCI), with a prevalence of 10% in the elderly [1]. Often, the progression of chronic cerebral ischemia is accompanied by motor and cognitive impairment, which leads to a decrease in the quality of life [2]. The study of the quality of life of patients is an important area in medicine due to its importance in assessing the effectiveness of treatment.

According to current data from foreign researchers, the incidence of moderate cognitive impairment of vascular origin ranges from 11 to 20% among the elderly [3]. The results of a study conducted in the Russian Federation revealed the incidence of non-dementia cognitive impairment at the level of 44%, while the risk of developing dementia in patients with mild cognitive impairment syndrome ranges from 3 to 26% [4, 5].

Despite the existing methods for the correction of vascular cognitive impairment, their effectiveness is still insufficient.

Based on the above, the high prevalence of cognitive impairment against the background of chronic cerebral ischemia with a tendency to a steady increase contributes to the search for new methods of treatment and prevention.

Purpose. To study the clinical and neurological characteristics of patients with chronic cerebral ischemia against the background of a combined course of hypertension and atherosclerosis, depending on the stage of the course.

Material and research methods. A comprehensive examination of 90 patients with chronic cerebral ischemia stages I, II and III on the background of arterial hypertension, cerebral atherosclerosis was carried out. The age of the patients was in the following interval - 56-84 years (mean age 69.7 ± 8.1). The diagnosis and stages of CCI were established using the criteria accepted in our country [1] based on the results of clinical, neurological, neuropsychological, and instrumental (duplex scanning, MRI of the brain) examinations of patients. The duration of the disease by the beginning of the examination of patients according to the anamnesis and analysis of medical records varied from 4 to 12 years, averaging 5.7 ± 0.8 years.

Criteria for inclusion of patients in the study: age from 56 to 84 years; the presence of CCI I,II and III stages of hypertensive, atherosclerotic, and mixed genesis; informed consent to participate in the study; secondary or higher education.

Exclusion criteria: the presence of non-vascular encephalopathy; severe somatic (renal, liver, heart failure in the stage of decompensation), mental, hematological, oncological diseases; vasculitis; past strokes, craniocerebral injuries, infectious diseases of the central nervous system; use during the last 6 months of therapy that can distort the results of the examination (anxiolytics, antidepressants).

Clinical-neurological and instrumental research methods were used.

Material and research methods. In accordance with the goal and objectives, all examined patients were divided into 3 groups depending on the stage of CCI. Group I consisted of 30 patients with CCI I, mean age 63.1 ± 5.1 years, including 13 men (43.3%) and 17 women (57.7%) (hereinafter, the percentage is calculated from the number of patients in this group), the ratio of men: women was 0.8:1.0. Group II included 30 patients with CCI II with an average age of 74.2 ± 8.4 years, including 16 men (53.3%) and 14 women (46.7%) (the male:female ratio was 1.1: 1.0). III included 30 patients with CCI III aged 79.6 ± 9.4 , of which 12 were men and 18 were women (the ratio of men : women was 0.7:1.0). The control group (CG) included 20 patients, 10 men and 10 women, mean age 63.1 ± 6.4 years.

Clinical-neurological and instrumental research methods were used.

Survey result. All patients presented complaints typical of cerebrovascular pathology. Complaints of patients of group I were presented either in the form of individual symptoms of headache, dizziness, memory loss, mental performance,

headache, dizziness, noise in the head. Patients were also worried about sleep disturbance, irritability, increased tearfulness.

In group II, there was a tendency to an increase in the frequency of dizziness, memory loss, fatigue, there were complaints of an organic nature (speech impairment - bradylalia, dysarthria; impaired coordination and active movements - unsteadiness when walking, handwriting changes, oligokinesia, and others). Patients of group III in most cases did not report complaints due to reduced criticism. In this subgroup, organic complaints increased, worsening the quality of social and living conditions (Table 1).

Table 1

Complaints of patients with CCI

Complaints	group I		group II		group III	
	abc	%	abc	%	abc	%
Headache	23	76,7%	30	100,0%	3	10,0%
Dizziness	5	16,7%	9	30,0%	2	6,7%
Noise in ears	12	40,0%	19	63,3%	4	13,3%
Decreased memory	8	26,7%	22	73,3%	3	10,0%
Fatigue	16	53,3%	25	83,3%	5	16,7%
Sleep disturbance	13	43,3%	19	63,3%	6	20,0%
Irritability	16	53,3%	23	76,7%	5	16,7%
Emotional lability	17	56,7%	21	70,0%	4	13,3%
Speech disorder	0	0,0%	2	6,7%	15	50,0%
Movement disorder	0	0,0%	5	16,7%	18	60,0%
Impaired coordination	0	0,0%	7	23,3%	17	56,7%

The neurological status was assessed in patients with CCI. Scattered neurological symptoms were more common in groups II and III in the form of instability in the Rombreg position, changes in superficial and deep reflexes (in the form of their increase on the one hand), the appearance of pyramidal insufficiency in the form of Babinski's symptom, and reflexes of oral automatism. In subgroup III, ocular disorders in the form of anisocoria, gaze paresis were more common (Table 2).

Part of the patients 27.8% (n=25) were examined by a psychiatrist as prescribed by the attending physician. Concomitant diseases identified by this specialist are presented in Table 3.

In the vast majority, no delineated psychiatric nosology is characteristic of the early stages of CNMC, and a different spectrum of organic disorders of behavior, mood, and personality is clearly demonstrated in the advanced stages.

Table 2

Changes in neurological status in patients with CCI.

Neurological status	group I		group II		group III	
	abc	%	abc	%	Abc	%
Nystagmus	1	3,3%	0	0,0%	6	20,0%
Anisocoria	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	3,3%
Facial asymmetry	0	0,0%	12	40,0%	23	76,7%
Tongue deviation	0	0,0%	8	26,7%	21	70,0%
Decreased muscle strength	0	0,0%	15	50,0%	25	83,3%
Movement disorder	0	0,0%	8	26,7%	21	70,0%
Changing reflexes	2	6,7%	12	40,0%	26	86,7%
pyramid signs	2	6,7%	5	16,7%	19	63,3%
Instability in the Romberg position	2	6,7%	9	30,0%	24	80,0%

Table 3

Concomitant psychiatric nosology in patients with CCI

Psychiatric nosology	group I		group II		group III	
	abc	%	abc	%	abc	%
organic anxiety disorder, F06.4	3	10,0%	7	23,3%	10	33,3%
organic mixed affective disorder F06.33	1	3,3%	4	13,3%	6	20,0%
organic emotionally labile disorder, F06.6	4	13,3%	9	30,0%	3	10,0%

organic personality disorder, F07.0	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	23	76,7%
vascular dementia, F01	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	30	100,0%

In patients with CCI, using clear criteria of Russian recommendations [1], a cardiologist identified background cardiological pathology under the ICD-10 heading "Diseases of the circulatory system" in groups I, II and III of patients: Essential arterial hypertension (I10) - 60.0%, 70.0% and 86.7%, respectively; hypertensive coronary heart disease - (I11) - 20.0%, 40.0% and 80.0%, respectively; non-stenosing atherosclerosis of the brachiocephalic arteries (BCA) (I 67.2) - 40.0%, 56.7% and 20.0%, respectively; stenosing atherosclerosis of BCA (I 170) - 0.0% 23.3% and 80.0%, respectively (Table 4).

Table 4

Background cardiac pathology in patients with CCI

Background cardiac pathology	group I		group II		group III	
	abc	%	abc	%	abc	%
essential arterial hypertension, I 10	18	60,0%	21	70,0%	26	86,7%
hypertensive ischemic heart disease, I 11	6	20,0%	12	40,0%	24	80,0%
non-stenosing atherosclerosis of brachiocephalic arteries, I 67.2	12	40,0%	17	56,7%	6	20,0%
stenosing atherosclerosis of brachiocephalic arteries, I 170	0	0,0%	7	23,3%	24	80,0%

Conclusion

Thus, among patients with CCI, women predominated slightly - 59 people (53.6%), the gender index was - men-women - 0.9:10. During the clinical and neurological examination, it was revealed that with the progression of CCI, complaints become more pronounced and at the advanced stages a different spectrum of organic disorders of behavior, mood, and personality is clearly

demonstrated. From this it should be concluded that the prevention of the progression of cerebrovascular insufficiency against the background of the combined course of hypertension and atherosclerosis should be started in the early stages of the formation of this syndrome.

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